

Course: ANTH 229
Skeletal Anatomy
Class Time: Tuesday/Thursday
10:30–11:45 AM
Instructor: Dr Jess Beck
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Santiago Caruso – Wunderkammer

Knowledge of human osteology is key for fields such as archaeology, biological anthropology, forensic anthropology, anatomy, and medicine. This six-week course provides an introduction to skeletal anatomy for anthropologists and biologists, and covers the entire human skeleton, with sections on growth, development, and pathology. The skeletal anatomy of select non-human mammals is used to demonstrate the functional morphology of each bone. At the end of this course, students are able to identify individual bones (complete and fragmentary), recognize bone landmarks, describe normal and abnormal growth processes (including common mutations), and assess bones for signs of pathology. This class is a pre-requisite for ANTH 239: Forensic Anthropology and Bioarchaeology.

Learning Outcomes

- Identify individual bones
- Recognize features and landmarks; understand how bones articulate
- Describe normal and abnormal growth processes
- Examine bones for signs of pathology

Class Behavior

This class includes handling real human bones and looking at images of dead bodies. All students are expected to maintain high levels of professionalism in this course, which includes respect for the dead and for each other. You may not take personal photos of the real human remains. You may not handle food or drink while working with the remains. Any disrespectful behaviors will result in a penalty on your overall course grade and may result in removal from the course.

Readings

Students must purchase their own copy (paper or electronic) of the following textbook so that it can be used in class. Any additional readings will be posted on Moodle or provided as paper copies.

Steele, D. Gentry and Claud A. Bramblett
1988 *The Anatomy and Biology of the Human Skeleton*. Texas A&M University Press. College Station, TX.

Grading

Your grade in this course will be based on four primary components:

Engagement (20%)	Quizzes (15%)
Exams (50%)	Bone Notebook (15%)

Final course grades will be assigned using a 100-point scale. Vassar does not assign a grade of A+; an “A” grade is ≥ 95 points. A failing grade is ≤ 62 points. Grades will be rounded up or down to the nearest integer.

A- = 90-94

B+ = 87-89

B = 83-86

B- = 80-82

C+ = 77-79

C = 73-76, etc., etc.

COVID-19 NOTE: I recognize that we are living through a global pandemic and that as a result there may be times during the semester when you need to quarantine or miss a class for COVID-related reasons. I will be as flexible as possible when making accommodations. If you require accommodations for COVID-related reasons, please let me know as soon as possible and we will find a way for you to make up the work.

Schedule of Quizzes, Exams & Notebook Due Date

Assignment	Date
Quiz 1: Anatomical Terminology, Bone Biology & Ethics	Tuesday, February 23
Quiz 2: Skull + Teeth	Tuesday, March 2
Quiz 3: Spine, Chest, Shoulder Girdle + Arm & Forearm	Tuesday, March 9
Quiz 4: Wrist, Hand, Fingers + Pelvic Girdle	Tuesday, March 16
Exam 1	Tuesday, March 23
Bone Notebook Due	Thursday, April 8
Exam 2	Thursday, April 8

Grading Structure

Engagement (20%): A weekly attendance sheet will circulate that in-person students are required to sign. It is your responsibility to sign the attendance sheet—if you are not able to do so at the beginning of class, you are responsible for asking for the attendance sheet at the end of class. However, simply showing up is not sufficient to achieve the full 20%. Active demonstration that you are engaged with the course material, including participating in labs, contributing to class discussion, and diligently working on your Bone Notebook over the course of the semester will also be factored into this grade.

Quizzes (15%): There are four quizzes which will occur on the first meeting of the week and will take approximately 15 minutes of class time. Quizzes are worth 5% each and your lowest

quiz grade will be dropped. These weekly quizzes will cover material learned the preceding week and will range in structure from multiple choice, feature identification, and practical applications of knowledge learned during the course. Treat these quizzes as practice for your midterm and final exams—they are an opportunity for you to test your skills under time pressure and identify areas that you need to work on. There are over 200 bones in the human body; cramming is a bad strategy.

Bone Notebook (15%): Sketching individual elements from several different views is a key strategy that helps novice osteologists identify features while increasing their familiarity with the human skeleton. Time will be set aside to sketch the bones or teeth we are learning; these notebooks will also act as useful repositories for identification and siding tricks and as comprehensive notes for review before exams. At the end of the course, your notebooks will be collected and graded. A detailed guide to your bone notebooks is provided on the first day of class and is available as a pdf on Moodle.

Exams (50%): There will be two exams in this course; the exams will incorporate a variety of question formats, including visual identification of bones, multiple choice, and written responses. The exams are worth 25% each.

Office Hours

Office hours will be held on Zoom from 12:30–2:30 every Thursday, with additional Zoom office hours scheduled by appointment for students who cannot make that time slot. To attend office hours, please make an appointment on my [Google Calendar](#) so that multiple students are not trying to meet with me simultaneously. A link to the Google Appointments page for office hours is posted on Moodle. Appointment slots will be for 20-minute increments. If you think that you will need more time to discuss a particular issue, please email me in advance.

Plagiarism Policy

In this course you will collaborate with other students during activities and participate in group discussions where other students' ideas will not doubt affect your own. However, in your own worksheets and written assignments, do not submit someone else's words or ideas as your own. Plagiarism will result in a zero on the offending assignment and more egregious cases will incur stronger penalties in accordance with Vassar academic policy. You can read the guidelines on Integrity of Academic Work in the Vassar College Regulations available online here: <https://deanofthecollege.vassar.edu/documents/college-regulations/VassarCollegeRegulations.pdf>

Accessibility Accommodations

If you have a condition that requires special accommodations, please have it documented by the Office for Accessibility and Educational Opportunity and provide me with a copy of your AEO accommodation letter before your accommodations are needed.

Title IX Responsibilities

All Vassar faculty members are “responsible employees;” if you inform a member of the faculty about a situation involving sexual harassment, sexual assault, relationship abuse, or stalking, they must share that information with the Title IX Coordinator. After a notification, the Title IX office will only provide outreach by email, meaning that you will control how your case will be handled—you do not have to read or reply to the email. It is entirely your decision whether or not to pursue a formal complaint.

VIRTUAL RESOURCES

At times this semester we may need to think outside the box and get creative about learning osteology. These are resources you can use to hone and practice your skills outside of lab.

**John Hawks Laboratory (UW Madison) –
Virtual Labs in Biological Anthropology**

JOHN HAWKS LABORATORY
Human evolution and genetics

<https://hominin.anthropology.wisc.edu/virtual-labs.html>

A variety of virtual anthropology labs are available on this website, which is of particular utility for students interested in biological anthropology and paleoanthropology. The first five labs—Regions of the Skeleton, Regions of the Cranium, Morphology of the Femur, Morphology of the Pelvis, and Pelvic Sexual Dimorphism—are useful resources for both ANTH 229 and ANTH 239.

eSkeletons (University of Texas at Austin)

<http://eskeletons.org/>

eSkeletons is an online osteology database aimed at teaching skeletal anatomy. It allows you to filter by species, specimen, bone, and view. This is an excellent resource for the comparative anatomy of primates. For example, if you want to compare photographs of a human hamate (one of the bones in the wrist) to a gibbon hamate, you can easily do so using the eSkeletons database.

Digitized Diseases (University of Bradford)

<http://www.digitiseddiseases.org/alpha/>

“an open access resource featuring human bones which have been digitised using 3D laser scanning, CT and radiography. The resource focuses on a wide range of pathological type specimens from archaeological and historical medical collections, specifically examples of chronic diseases which affect the human skeleton for which many of the physical changes are often not directly observable within clinical practice. [Includes] high fidelity photo-realistic digital representations of 3D bones that can be viewed, downloaded and manipulated on their computer, tablet or smartphone.” This is fantastic for students interested in bioarchaeology, especially skeletal pathology and trauma. Caveat: As of February 2021 the site is experiencing some glitches due to a server upgrade.

MorphoSource BETA

Morphosource (Duke University)

<https://www.morphosource.org/>

Morphosource compiles 2D and 3D data from a variety of museums, researchers, and colleges for a wide variety of species. As of February 2021, Morphosource has 235 human scans, and you can zoom and rotate the scans in their online portal. For quick reference, here is the taxonomic categorization of humans:

Kingdom–Animalia | Phylum–Chordata | Class–Mammalia | Order–Primates

Family–Hominidae | Genus–Homo | Species–sapiens

Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History 3D Collection

Smithsonian
National Museum of Natural History

<https://3d.si.edu/collections/hominin-fossils>

The Smithsonian has a 3D collection of CT or laser-scanned artifacts, fossils, and animals that you can view, rotate, and interact with on their website. The full collection can be found here <https://humanorigins.si.edu/evidence/3d-collection>, and the hominin fossils are linked above. The fossil scans are all of crania or mandibles, and there are a few specimens of Homo sapiens in the collection. This is a good site for students interested in biological anthropology, particularly paleoanthropology.

The Radiologist Instagram Page

<https://www.instagram.com/theradiologistpage>

Dr Naveen Sharma—a UK-based Consultant Radiologist—provides a resource that helps anyone learn more about radiology. Radiographs are labelled in detail, and there are lots of memes! This is a useful resource for students considering pre-med or a career in radiology.

Human Osteology Resources (Wichita State University)

<https://libraries.wichita.edu/c.php?g=120021&p=782022>

WICHITA STATE
UNIVERSITY

This library page lists a variety of resources for learning osteology and can be used to further your interests in anatomy, human biology, paleopathology, and radiology.

3D4MEDICAL from ELSEVIER

3D 4 Medical (Elsevier)

<https://3d4medical.com/>

NOTE: COSTS \$35 FOR ANNUAL STUDENT LICENSE. I downloaded the free trial of this recently and it is a wonderfully detailed virtual resource that allows you to examine and rotate individual elements, and add layers of connective tissue muscle, nerves, blood, etc. Key features and muscle attachment sites are identified for each bone. A particularly useful resource for students following the pre-med track.

Class Schedule and Reading List

Note: The readings assigned for a particular day should be read **before** that day, to ensure that you are prepared for the discussion or activities. I reserve the right to change the readings, activities, and discussion if I believe such a change is pertinent to our safety and/or the direction of the course.

Week 1: Anatomical Terminology, Bone Biology & Ethics

Thursday, February 18

Topic: Bone Biology, Anatomical Terminology & the Ethics of Working with the Dead

Reading(s): Bernstein, 2018; Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 1: Introduction to the Study of the Human Skeleton + Chapter 2: Bone Biology (16 pp.)

Week 2: The Skull & Teeth

Tuesday, February 23

QUIZ 1

Topic: The Skull

Reading(s): Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 3: The Skull (49 pp.)

Thursday, February 25

Topic: The Teeth

Reading(s): Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 4: The Dentition (40 pp.)

Week 3: The Spine, Chest & Shoulder Girdle + The Arm & Forearm

Tuesday, March 2

QUIZ 2

Topic: The Spine, Chest & Shoulder Girdle

Reading(s): Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 5: The Vertebral Column + Chapter 6: The Chest and Shoulder Girdle (41 pp.)

Thursday, March 4

Topic: The Arm & Forearm

Reading(s): Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 7: The Arm (19 pp.)

Week 4: The Wrist, Hand & Fingers + The Pelvic Girdle

Tuesday, March 9

QUIZ 3

Topic: + The Wrist, Hand, and Fingers

Reading(s): Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 8: The Wrist, Hand, and Fingers (16 pp.)

Thursday, March 12

Topic: The Pelvic Girdle

Reading(s): Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 9: The Pelvic Girdle (25 pp.)

Week 5: The Thigh, Leg, Ankle & Foot

Tuesday, March 16

QUIZ 4

Topic: The Thigh and Leg

Reading(s): Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 10: The Leg

Thursday, March 18

Topic: The Ankle & Foot

Reading(s): Steele & Bramblett, Chapter 11: The Ankle, Foot, and Toes

Week 6: Exam 1 + Comparative Functional Anatomy

Tuesday, March 23

EXAM 1

Thursday, March 25

Topic: Comparative Functional Anatomy

Reading(s): Beisaw 2013 (55 pp.)

Week 7: Growth, Development, and Pathologies

Tuesday, March 30

Topic: Growth, Development, and Pathologies

Reading(s): White and Folkens, 2005; Scheuer and Black 2004 (42 pp.)

MID-SEMESTER RECESS MARCH 31 – APRIL 4

Week 8: Class Recap & Exam 2 Review

Tuesday, April 6

Topic: Class Recap & Exam 2 Review

Reading(s): None

Thursday, April 8

EXAM 2

ANTH 229 Bone Notebook Due

Reading List

Beisaw, April. "What Bone Is It?" in *Identifying and Interpreting Animal Bones: A Manual*, 47–102. College Station: Texas A&M University Press, 2013.

Bernstein, Robin Eileen. "The Skeleton in My Closet." *New York Times*. May 18, 2018.
<https://www.nytimes.com/2018/05/18/well/family/the-skeleton-in-my-closet.html>
(accessed 15 February 2021).

Scheuer, Louise, and Sue Black. "Juvenile Skeletal Remains: Provenance, Identification, and Interpretation," in *The Juvenile Skeleton*, 1–22. London: Elsevier Academic Press, 2004.

White, Tim and Pieter Folkens. "Osteological & Dental Pathology," in *The Human Bone Manual*, 309–332. Boston: Elsevier Academic Press, 2005.

Bone Broke Blog

Back when I was in grad school and appear to have had ridiculous amounts of time on my hands, I maintained a blog. I haven't written any new posts for years, but the blog contains a vast repository of osteological and bioarchaeological information, generally conveyed in a light-hearted or humorous manner that is intended to help novice practitioners remember complex osteological terminology and morphology. I still return to some of my siding and identification posts when I am in the field and refreshing my own osteological knowledge. The blog is can be found here www.bonebroke.org. I have identified a number of relevant posts below, categorized by section.

Anatomical Terminology

Standard Anatomical Position: [Bioarch Vocab: SAP](#)

Abduction and Adduction: [Bioarch Vocab: Abduction and Adduction](#)

Supination: [Bioarch Vocab: Supination](#)

Features and Pathology

Glenoid fossa: Bioarch Vocab: [Glenoid Fossa](#)

Nutrient foramen: [Bioarch Vocab: Nutrient Foramen](#)

Caries: Bioarch Vocab: [Caries](#)

Calculus: [Bioarch Vocab: Calculus](#)

Skull

Splanchnocranium: [Bioarch Vocab: Splanchnocranium](#)

Temporal: [Osteomenagerie 3: The petrous portion of the temporal bone](#)

Temporal: [Palpable anatomy: How to identify and side an isolated zygomatic process](#)

Parietals: [How to identify and side parietal bones](#)

Teeth

All teeth: [Identifying human teeth: Human dentition cheat sheet](#)

Vertebral Column

Vertebrae: [Osteomenagerie 7: The Vertebrae](#)

Vertebrae: [Cake or...superior articular facets?](#)

Chest & Shoulder Girdle

Ribs: [Orienting and siding regular ribs](#)

Pelvic Girdle

Innominate: [Hip hip hooray: Orienting and identifying features of the os coxae](#)

Arm, Wrist & Hand

Humerus: [Feeling shafted? Tips for identifying humeral shaft fragments](#)

Radius: [That's so rad: Identifying and siding the radius](#)

Phalanges: [Gotta hand it to you: identifying manual and pedal phalanges](#)

Scaphoid: [Osteomenagerie 2: The scaphoid](#)

Lunate: [In Honor of the "Super Moon" – Identifying and siding the lunate](#)

Carpals: [Osteomenagerie 4: The capitate](#)

Pisiform: [Osteomenagerie 5: The pisiform](#)

Hamate: [Identifying and siding the hamate](#)

Leg, Ankle & Foot

Tibia: [Tibial pursuit: How to identify and side the tibia](#)

Femur: [Get a leg up on the competition: Tips for identifying femoral shaft fragments](#)

Patella: [A guide to quickly siding the patella](#)

Navicular: [Osteomenagerie 1: The navicular](#)

Calcaneus: [Osteomenagerie 6: Tips for siding the calcaneus](#)

Cuneiforms: [Merely a cuneiformity: Identifying and siding the cuneiforms](#)

Pedal Phalanges: [Gotta hand it to you: identifying manual and pedal phalanges](#)